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UNIFIED THREAT MANAGEMENT VETERAN - A CASE STUDY ON CYBEROAM TECHNOLOGIES PVT. LTD.

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Abstract

Cyberoam Technologies Pvt Ltd is a veteran company involved in the area of Unified Threat Management Systems. It was founded by Ben Casado and Hemal Patel as a division of Elitecore Technologies at Ahmedabad in 1999. Unified threat management is an appliance or virtual machine that combines multiple security aspects such as Antivirus, Intrusion prevention system, Firewall, Anti-spam to safeguard the network and computers of the enterprise. Cyberoam Technologies manufactures and sells Unified threat management appliances which comprising of Antivirus, Spam filter, Web filter, Application Firewall, intrusion prevention system etc. Cyberoam UTM's are also known as Next-generation Firewalls. The Layer 8 technology from Cyberoam enables network access based on identity and role. UTM devices are widely used by companies, educational institutions, small and medium-sized enterprises to protect their internal network from external threats, to shape their bandwidth utilization, to track and control Internet usage, etc. Some of the products developed by Cyberoam Technologies include Cyberoam Unified threat management appliances, Cyberoam iView, Cyberoam Central Console and Cyberoam NetGenie. Cyberoam unified threat management device is designed to meet all the relevant regulatory compliance requirements such as HIPAA, CIPA, PCI-DSS, ISO 27001, GLBA, etc. Cyberoam has a presence in over 125 countries and a strong customer base of over 60,000 users around the world. Their full-fledged customer support and software development and research wing operates from India. The total workforce of the company was more than 550 worldwide prior to the acquisition by Sophos. In 2014, Cyberoam was acquired by Sophos, a UK company. Post-acquisition Cyberoam and Sophos merged their international research and development activities to offer quicker product growth. We analyze product development strategies of Cyberoam Technologies in this case study along with product / service strategy, CSR strategy, marketing strategy, and security strategy. Some suggestions to promote sustainable development are also presented based on the SWOT analysis.

Keywords: Cyberoam, UTM, Unified Threat management, Layer 8, Sophos, Next Generation Firewall.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Being exposed to the internet, puts computer systems at high risk due to the wide range of threats that exists in the internet. Some of the threats such as viruses, spyware, ransomware, adware etc are intended to exploit vulnerabilities in devices that are connected to the Internet. Compromised devices poses further risk as it acts according to the instructions of intruder. As Firewall alone cannot fight against modern day threats there was a need to have Intruder detection system, intruder prevention system, Antivirus, Anti malware systems etc at the gateway level to safeguard the underlying network from different kind of attacks. Introduction of Unified threat Management (UTM) systems replaced all these individual security applications with a single device which could be physical or virtual appliance. Unified threat management (UTM) system comprises multiple security services like IPS, content filtering, Denial of Service protection, Web Application firewall, antispam engine etc. Cyberoam UTM is one of the popular UTM device developed by a division of Indian based company named Elitecore Technologies situated at Ahmedabad, Gujrat [1]. Cyberoam was founded by Hemal Patel and Ben Casado in 1999. Soon it became number one vendor among the UTM appliance manufacturer community in India. Eventually it grown up as a leader in the field of Network Security Appliances globally. Elitecore Technologies also has presence in United States of America and Middle East. Research and Development center and Customer support center is situated in India. In 2014, Cyberoam was acquired by Sophos, a UK based security related hardware and Software Company. Cyberoam UTM deployments spanning over 90 countries in various sectors such as healthcare, insurance, banking, information technology, government organization, etc. make it a global enterprise [2].

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

We analyze product development strategies of Cyberoam Technologies in this case study along with product / service strategy, CSR strategy, marketing strategy, and security strategy [3-5]. Some suggestions to promote sustainable development are also presented based on the SWOT analysis.

3. METHODOLOGY :

This case study has been carried out based on the secondary data gathered from publications, journals, conference proceedings, Company websites, Research network websites, Focus group discussions, Various Analysis Frameworks like SWOT Analysis, Competitive Analysis, the Internet articles, prior research paper etc

4. PRODUCTS AND SOLUTIONS :

Cyberoam products and solutions provides robust perimeter security against modern day Internet threat like Trojans, Spywares, pharming and Viruses etc[6]. The products offered by Cyberoam include,

- **Unified Threat Management (UTM)**

Cyberoam UTM's available in the form of physical appliances as well as virtual machines. UTM Devices are available in the range of CR15i which is sufficient for small office to CR1500ia best fit for large enterprises. Various security features like AntiVirus, AntiSpam, Web Application Firewall, Content and Application filters etc are integrated into a single

appliance known as UTM. These security features in UTM device functions on subscription basis [7].

- **Next Generation Firewall**

Cyberoam NG series appliances provide organizations with next-generation security features to secure emerging threats. Layer 8 identity based technology helps administrators to track user activity, bandwidth utilization etc [8].

- **Cyberoam NetGenie**

Cyberoam NetGenie is a best fit for small offices and Home office. NetGenie provides features such as Internet security via Firewall, IPS, access controls and small office VPN security [9].

- **Cyberoam Central Console (CCC)**

As hardware appliances, the Cyberoam Central Console (CCC) helps companies to centrally manage UTMs and other security devices commissioned in different locations [10].

- **Cyberoam iView**

An in-depth visibility tool for network and user activities. iView presents logs based on various compliance requirements such as PCIDSS, ISO27001 etc. This tool can also be used effectively for Forensic Analysis [11].

5. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY :

Cyberoam Technologies Private Limited's key corporate responsibility is to uphold its corporate principles through its determination to evolve in a both social and environmental responsible manner, while at the same time meeting the needs of its stake holders. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Policy mandates the Company to spend minimum 2 percent of the company's average net financial gain in the immediately preceding 3 financial years on an annual basis [12]. The surplus arising from CSR initiatives or services or events should not be considered as a part of the company's corporate profit. All expenditure pertaining to CSR projects recommended by the CSR committee and approved by the Board shall be included in the CSR expenditure.

6. MARKETING STRATEGY :

Since its inception, Cyberoam has had a full-fledged marketing strategy in place to emerge as a number one player on the Indian UTM market. Cyberoam has expanded its reach beyond A Class City by developing strong sales relationships with national partners such as AGC, many major regional distributors, and authorized channel partners. [13]

7. SECURITY STRATEGY :

Security architecture for companies is becoming increasingly complicated when trying to balance the needs of employees, compliance requirements and client's expectations. Rapid internet threat evolution demands advanced and sophisticated security solutions in place without burdening employees or businesses. Cyberoam's security strategy makes it easy to fit into any corporate network and provide end-to-end protection against the threat environment of the

organization. Most of the organization fails to realize that the risks arises from internal resources need to be handled with equal importance and care when comparing to external threats. All the activities of users pertaining to network gets recorded by Cyberoam and Identity based approach ensures that user authenticates before getting access to the Internet. Confidential information is protected by implementing segmentations using Zone based approach. Cyberoam ensures threat free VPN communication by implementing a bunch of security features like antimalware scanning for VPN traffic, identity based controls etc. Ability to create Security policies based on users makes administrators life easier. Cyberoam has developed Application and Web filter module to facilitate the organization to track and control their users' complete application and web activity [14]. A reporting tool capable of producing and notifying real time and historical data contributes a lot to fight against the malwares, and Cyberoam has built-in reporting engine.

8. COMPETITORS :

There are many competitors out there on the market, but based on their success and technological innovations, we will list only a few [15].

a) WatchGuard

WatchGuard is Cyberoam's top competitor. WatchGuard was founded in 1996 and is based in Seattle, Washington, D.C. WatchGuard's system to offer the fastest performance when it counts with all security features turned on.

b) Endian

Endian is considered as one of the top rivals of Cyberoam. Endian was established in 2003 in Bolzano, Trentino-Alto Adige. Endian specializes in the software application sector.

c) Palo Alto Networks

The headquarters of Palo Alto Networks is situated in Santa Clara, California, and was established in 2005. Palo Alto Networks is in the software application industry.

d) FortiGate

FortiGate is designed to provide network security solution, threat protection and performance without much complicated technology.

e) Sonicwall

Sonicwall with more than one million deployments worldwide, protects networks from malware attack with the help of real-time breach detection technology.

f) Fortinet Unified Threat Management

Fortinet was established in 2000. FortiGate, a firewall, was the first product of the company. Fortinet launched its Security Fabric architecture in 2016, which included integration, automation with different network security tools and vendors of third parties

9. ANALYSIS :

From the date of inception Cyberoam Technology has focused mainly on continual improvement of its products. The extensive research and development activities carried out by intelligent researchers contributed towards the growth of the organization. Even though Cyberoam developed handful of products, all of them were undergoing frequent updates thereby keeping

them at par with the market requirement. 24X7 proactive customer support on Cyberoam product enabled the end users to tackle any issues pertaining to infrastructure, security etc much effectively. There were certain modules where Cyberoam OS was not able to provide consistent output. One of such module is IPsec site to site VPN which had performance stability issue on long run. Acquisition by Sophos increased Cyberoam's market value and opened opportunity to expand its reach in many foreign countries. As Cyberoam and Sophos combined their global research and development activities after the acquisition, increased the opportunity for faster product development and growth. While well-proven and profitable to date, Cyberoam faces challenges by selling products on a well-established network security sector. Also tight competition from upcoming and well established UTM keeps Cyberoam's developers on toes all the time.

10. SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER IMPROVEMENT :

Below suggestions are made to improve the overall performance and quality of service,

- Try to incorporate future requirements requested by end customers within a quarter.
- Maintain close relationship with the end customers and channel partners
- Strengthen entire product by fixing customer reported issues on priority basis there by stabilizing the network and security infrastructure

11. CONCLUSION :

In today's world, no organization can afford to take the risk of running a business without adequate precautions for network security. Industry is always looking for intelligent security solutions that can reduce their burden and enhance security measures. Cyberoam UTM easily fits in with this requirement and most standard requirements are met. After acquisition by Sophos, UTM's demand increased several times, expanding the additional customer base of the parent company. Continuous quality improvement and world-class customer support played a significant role behind Cyberoam products ' success. Cyberoam continues its success story even after having tight competitions from many UTM companies.

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